

The Effect of Game and Technology Addiction on Domestic Communication

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ABSTRACT

In the contemporary world, it is widely recognized that advancing technology has permeated all facets of our

existence, exerting its influence across several domains in an essential realm of knowledge. The use of technology in diverse domains such as job, school, family, and leisure has been acknowledged to have detrimental consequences that impact families and children. Technology addiction has a detrimental impact on individuals' mental and emotional well-being. Technology addiction may have a detrimental impact on family members and children, adversely impacting their social interactions, psychological well-being, and academic achievements. It is well recognized that this will decrease physical activity levels and transform individuals into socially isolated persons.

Keywords: *Family, Psychology , technology, Addiction, Education, Socialization*

INTRODUCTION

A family is a group of people who are connected through marriage, blood relations, or kinship and typically reside together in the same household. It serves as the fundamental unit where individuals' social, economic, sexual, and psychological needs are fulfilled, and their involvement and cohesion in society are maintained and governed (TDK, 2024).

The Turkish society is built around the fundamental principle of equality between couples, making the family the cornerstone of their culture. The government implements the required actions and creates the institution to safeguard the tranquility and well-being of the family, particularly by ensuring the safety of the mother and children, as well as promoting and enforcing family planning (Turkish Constitution, 1982).

The relationship between family and society is characterized by continuous contact, which may have positive or negative consequences. Societies are established by the consolidation of families. The fundamental composition of families has remained relatively constant across time, however there have been notable changes in the individuals comprising families and the

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allocation of their responsibilities. The extended family structure, prevalent before to the industrial revolution, was supplanted by the nuclear family unit comprising only of a father, mother, and their offspring in the aftermath of the industrial revolution. Consequently, there have been changes in the composition of families based on where they live.

Regardless of the specific structure of family, all families have distinct life stages, roles, and obligations that are shared among family members.

The family plays a significant role in society. The family is the primary and essential component in both societal and individual functioning. The family serves as the primary setting where individuals fulfill their fundamental requirements, including education, nutrition, care, psychological and emotional development, maintaining sound mental well-being, acquiring cultural values, and the need for love, all of which hold significant importance in their lives (TC Ministry of National Education, 2011).

Family relationships and the family environment are the primary contexts in which persons undergoing psychosocial development interact. This enables people to acquire a sense of identity, self-assurance, personal growth, affection, and esteem for themselves and others, enhance their social abilities, and adjust to society.

Families are categorized into seven divisions based on child-rearing practices, namely parent types and family types. The following items are:

AIM

The objective is to investigate the impact of technology and gaming addiction on family communication.

RESULTS

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Positive and Democratic Parenting Approach: In this perspective about family dynamics, when a family exhibits transparency, harmony, affection, reverence, and confidence, the kid is embraced in all dimensions. In addition to serving as role models for their children via their conduct, parents also act as advisers. These parents exercise guidance over their children while allowing them autonomy in decision-making. The youngster, who seeks resolutions to the challenges faced with their father and mother and gradually hones this ability, also experiences the repercussions of their decisions. Boundaries and regulations within the family are collectively established for all members. The youngster has freedom within these boundaries. Children raised with this methodology evolve into contented adults with enhanced problem-solving abilities, self-assurance, and robust personality development.

Inconsistent Parental Approach: Within these family structures, the child's conduct might be interpreted either negatively or favorably, depending on the parents' present psychological condition. The incongruent attitudes of parents towards their two children or the divergent views between parents might have a detrimental impact on the children. The youngster lacks the ability to anticipate which conduct is detrimental and which is beneficial. These youngsters often exhibit anxiety and discontentment within society.

Apathetic and Unconcerned Parenting Approach: In this family dynamic, it can be seen that there are negligent parents that exhibit apathetic and indifferent attitudes towards their child's conduct. In families of this kind, it is uncertain whether or not there is a kid present. Parents sometimes mistake tolerance with relinquishing control. If the kid does not cause any disruptions to the father and mother, they do not encounter any issues with their children. They often have a tendency to associate themselves with bad role models. They are also susceptible to developing detrimental and negative behaviors. These youngsters are likely to have challenges, particularly in their emotional connections, as adults and are very prone to encounter issues with forming attachments.

Oppressive and Authoritarian Family Approach: This family type is characterized by an absence of love and respect towards the kid, and instead, an oppressive attitude and rigorous

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punishment are prevalent. The kid lacks agency and independence. The family enforces strict penalties. Children raised in such situations may develop feelings of insecurity, timidity, tension, or anxiety. These youngsters are unable to form a close bond with their parents and may exhibit hostile conduct towards them. As adults, they may acquire a disposition towards criminal behavior, insecurity, lack of success in interpersonal relationships, anxiety, and overall lack of achievement.

Overly Protective Family Approach: These families grow up in a bubble to protect their children, and they tend to meet all the child's needs without the child expressing it. They do not allow the child to have a negative experience or to see the consequences of his actions, that is, to grow. Children growing up in such an environment can be people who cannot handle their work alone, are always dependent on others, and lack self-confidence.

Extremely Tolerant Family Approach: This family type may also be referred to as adaptable families. Within these households, rather of adhering to structure and regulations, the kid is granted unrestricted authority. The youngster has complete freedom, with no limitations or regulations put upon them, and is granted permission to pursue their desires without any restrictions. The child's desires are promptly fulfilled. These youngsters develop feelings of insecurity. Essentially, in order for a kid to have a sense of security, it is essential that they have well defined limits and regulations. Children who are brought up with such adaptability struggle to develop self-discipline. As individuals age, they may not only struggle to exhibit cooperative conduct in social settings, but may also face exclusion from the society.

Perfectionist Family Approach: These family types exhibit both stringent discipline and profound affection within the family unit. These families have high expectations of their children, demanding perfection and achievement in all areas. The child's choices, growth, habits, and desires lack support. Children brought up in such a familial setting may exhibit traits of low self-assurance and a fear of committing errors.

The relationship between family and society is characterized by continuous contact, which may have positive or negative consequences. Societies are created via the amalgamation of

families. The structure of the family has remained constant throughout time, but, there have been changes in the roles and responsibilities of its members. Prior to the industrial revolution, the extended family structure was prevalent. However, with the industrial revolution, the nuclear family, comprising of a mother, father, and their offspring, became the dominant family unit. Nevertheless, there were also changes in the composition of families based on their place of residence. Irrespective of the family type, families possess distinct stages of existence, roles, and obligations that are assigned to individual family members (Varan, 2011).

Types and Classification of Video Games

Multiple methodologies and categorization systems exist for categorizing video games and identifying their genres. The categories of games are often determined by factors such as the game's gameplay style, mechanics, theme, and plot. Nevertheless, every categorization system has its own merits and drawbacks, making it challenging to devise a universally applicable classification system. For instance, several categorizations are derived from the overall gameplay style of games. According to this methodology, games are categorized as FPS (First Person Shooter). It may be categorized into certain genres such as Shooter, RTS (Real-Time Strategy), and RPG (Role-Playing Game). Nevertheless, these categorizations may not comprehensively capture the intricate framework of some games. Another strategy is derived from the fundamental mechanics of the game. According to this methodology, games may include fundamental elements such as puzzle-solving, platforming, strategic decision-making, and combat. This categorization helps provide a more comprehensive explanation of the gameplay mechanics in games. Nevertheless, both approaches are incapable of offering an entirely conclusive categorization, and many games may include several genres or subgenres. Moreover, due to the dynamic nature of the game business, novel genres may arise or current genres may undergo alterations. Thus, the classification of gaming genres will always remain a contentious and unstable matter.

Video Game Genres Report

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Action Games

Action games are a genre that emphasizes physical obstacles, specifically designed to assess the player's hand-eye coordination and response speed. Typically, it is categorized into subgenres such as fighting, shooting, and platform games. Typically, the player exercises control of a protagonist or a vehicle/object. The primary objective is to achieve a range of tasks, including finishing certain levels, gathering power items, surmounting barriers, and vanquishing adversaries.

1-Adventure Games

Adventure games are a narrative-focused genre that encompasses features such as investigation, discovery, and problem-solving. This genre is mostly prevalent on the computer platform, while there are also adventure games available on consoles. Typically, players exercise control over a designated character and fulfill diverse goals to progress the narrative inside the game. For instance, Uncharted 3: Drake's Deception, the Tomb Raider series, and God of War are possible options.

2-Fighting Games

Fighting games are a genre characterized by players engaging in combat against each other with the objective of emerging victorious. Typically, players exert control of a character and engage in combat with adversaries. Within this particular genre, every character has distinct powers, and the game often comprises many rounds. Within the realm of fighting games, players have the ability to execute a multitude of combos in order to unleash unique and powerful strikes. As an example, we may provide the movies Heavyweight, released in 1976, Champ, and Karate Champ.

3-Platform Games

Platform games are a genre that enables players to advance by maneuvering their character over challenging platforms. Engaging in this activity often requires fundamental abilities such

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as leaping, sprinting, and problem-solving. Within this particular genre, players often advance through two-dimensional or three-dimensional environments and use diverse platforms to surmount obstacles. For instance, notable examples of video games are Super Mario Bros., Sonic the Hedgehog, and Celeste.

The purpose of this paper is to provide a comprehensive description of several video game genres and their distinctive characteristics. Each genre caters to distinct player expectations and offers unique experiences, contributing to the variety of the gaming business.

4-Puzzle Games

Puzzle games often include individual players who use their cognitive talents, such as intellect, reasoning, attention, and memory, to solve challenges. These puzzles assess players' problem-solving skills via various sorts of challenges. These sorts of puzzles are sometimes referred to as brain teasers. Puzzle games are a type of video games that revolve on the task of solving puzzles.

5-Simulation Games

Simulation games are a genre of video games that aim to accurately replicate real-life events. These games aim to simulate real-life situations in the form of a game for goals such as teaching, analysis, or prediction.

6-Role Playing Games (RPG)

Role-playing games are a broad category of games where participants take on the roles of various characters inside a fictitious setting. Players engage in narrative immersion by controlling characters that are developed within the confines of certain regulations.

7-Sports Games

Sports games provide a simulated environment that replicates a sports field. Typically, these games include many sports such as football, basketball, tennis, and rally. These games often

need proficiency in keyboard use and appeal to players due to their ability to replicate the sensation of realism.

8-Strategy Games

Strategy games may be categorized into two main types: real-time strategy games (RTS) and turn-based strategy games. In real-time strategy (RTS) games, players engage in continuous gameplay, without the need to wait for each other's turns. In the context of turn-based strategy games, players are required to wait for their opponent's move before they may make their own move. Prominent instances of such games include chess, Dune 2, Tycoon Series, Warcraft, Starcraft, Age Of Empires, and Hearts of Iron 4.

9-Logical Games

Logical games are games where players may advance by performing certain logical computations. While some publications may refer to it as a video game genre, there is in fact no official game genre of that name.

10-Online Games

Online games are interactive games that may be accessed and played over the internet. These games often have multiplayer features and encompass titles like World of Warcraft, Knight Online, and Metin 2.

11-Math Games

Math games are categorized as a blend of several genres and are not explicitly classified as a genre of video games..

12-Educational Games

Educational games are games that are expressly intended for the aim of education. In these games, the knowledge or behavior that has to be learnt is included into the game in a way that

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allows the learner to acquire it. Additionally, there are instructional games specifically created to assist with school classes.

What are the positive effects of digital games?

Digital games include several beneficial impacts. Here are a few examples:

1. Facilitates active, hands-on, and inquiry-based learning: Players are required to engage in active thinking and experimentation in order to answer the difficulties presented in the game. This fosters the acquisition of information and facilitates the implementation of that knowledge in actual situations.
2. Enhances autonomous and analytical thinking abilities: Players are required to use analytical thinking and make independent decisions in order to overcome the obstacles presented in the game.
3. Demands the application of preexisting knowledge: Certain games need players to recall and use knowledge they have previously acquired, hence facilitating the practical application of learnt information.
4. Enhances cognitive abilities via the exploration of various strategies: Games foster problem-solving by encouraging players to experiment with diverse ways, so enhancing their learning skills.
5. Enhances proficiency in managerial control, planning, and recall: Certain games, such as strategy games, may assist players in honing their abilities in managing tasks and making strategic decisions.
6. Enhances multitasking and cognitive abilities: Certain games need players to concurrently handle many tasks, hence enhancing their multitasking and reasoning abilities.

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7. Facilitates learning across several academic domains: Games designed for diverse disciplines, such as mathematics, physics, foreign language, and information technologies, may enhance students' motivation and facilitate their learning process.
8. Offers rapid response opportunities: Certain games need fast reactions, hence enhancing reflexes.
9. Enhances concentration and visual-attention abilities: Games may assist players in enhancing their concentration and visual-attention abilities.
10. Multiplayer games facilitate the development of social strategies, since players have the opportunity to enhance their social aptitude via collaborative group effort.
11. Enhances digital literacy: Early exposure to computer games may foster the development of digital literacy abilities in children.
12. Certain games may aid in the treatment of hereditary illnesses, such as autism, by supporting therapeutic processes.
13. Enhances feelings of accomplishment and boosts self-assurance: Players get a sense of achievement and elevate their self-confidence by overcoming challenges inside the game.
14. Alleviates weariness and tension, enhances self-assurance: Certain games have the ability to alleviate players' exhaustion, diminish stress, and enhance their self-assurance.

The good impacts of digital games manifest when played with mindfulness and moderation. It is crucial to ensure that the games are not too abundant and are acceptable for the corresponding age demographic.

What is Addiction?

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Addiction is a multifaceted disorder that arises from the interplay of several causes (Straussner, 2004). The creation process of addiction is influenced by a range of elements that a person has been exposed to from infancy, including familial, social and cultural features, the environment they live in, and their unique traits. This procedure should be approached with a comprehensive and all-encompassing method.

Addiction is defined as the state of lacking control over one's actions. The individual has a loss of ability to regulate their use of a drug, specifically alcohol, an item, or a certain habit. Withdrawal symptoms, such as restlessness, sleeplessness, and irritability, arise when the frequency of use or behavior is decreased or stopped. (Ögel, 2018; Yeşilay Publications, 2018). For an extended period, addiction has been seen as a moral dilemma or a deficiency in determination caused by a lack of willpower. Individuals with addiction were historically stigmatized as having poor moral character and being unable to lead a virtuous life or regulate their actions. As a result of this misinterpretation, individuals with addiction issues have been marginalized and subjected to social stigma.

Nevertheless, progress in neuroscience and behavioral research has definitively refuted this idea. Currently, addictions are recognized as a persistent neurological disorder. Addictions are characterized as a chronic condition that advances through periods of recovery and relapse, but does not achieve complete healing.

Addiction is the persistent use of a drug, accompanied by an inability to cease despite the intention to do so. This circumstance persists despite its adverse effects on emotional, bodily, or social well-being. At the neuroscientific level, addiction leads to both structural and functional alterations in the brain, making it a challenging condition to address.

According to the DSM 5 Diagnostic Criteria Reference Manual, the addiction criteria are as follows :

Prolonged usage beyond the specified duration

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Prior failed cessation efforts

Devoting the majority of your time on locating and using drugs

Persisting in use despite detrimental consequences and damage.

Substance use desire

The tolerance is progressively rising due to the insufficient quantity of the chemical taken.

Deprivation

According to the American Psychiatric Association, addiction may arise from either pharmacological or behavioral factors. Chemical addictions often originate when an individual consciously chooses to use a chemical, but gradually loses the ability to regulate their usage. The individual is unable to refrain from taking drugs, while being aware of the negative impact it has on their everyday functioning.

When addiction occurs, there are changes in both the structure and functioning of the brain. These alterations may lead to disturbances in mood, cognition, and conduct. Neuroimaging studies reveal that addiction is associated with impairments in brain regions involved in cognitive functions like as judgment, decision-making, learning, memory, and behavioral regulation.

When combating addiction, it is crucial to take into account all the impacts encountered by the person and embrace a comprehensive strategy. Psychosocial support, family therapy, and individual therapy are viable methods that may be used in the therapeutic process. Additionally, it is crucial to enhance public awareness and implement preventive measures to combat addiction.

How Does Addiction Occur?

Addiction is an intricate phenomenon that arises from the interplay of several causes. Psychological, biological, and environmental variables are significant contributors to the development of addiction. Below are few elements that influence the development of addiction:

Genetic Predisposition : An individual's susceptibility to addiction is influenced by genetic variables (Borsos, 2009). Individuals with a familial predisposition to addiction are more susceptible to developing addiction.

Environmental Effects: An individual's surroundings may heighten the likelihood of developing addiction (Volkow, 2010; Bevilacqua, 2009). Embracing addiction as commonplace, particularly within the family or a setting that promotes addiction, might heighten the probability of a person acquiring addicted.

Biological Factors: Chemical imbalances in the brain and the impact of neurotransmitters like dopamine are significant factors in the formation of addiction. Specific chemicals have the ability to alter the chemical composition of the brain, leading to the initiation of addictive behaviors (Bromberg et al., 2010).

Psychological well-being: The presence of psychological issues, such as stress, sadness, and anxiety, might heighten the likelihood of developing addiction (Hamamcı, Şahin, Türk, 2022).

Impact of Substance or Behavior: drug addiction may lead to an elevation in dopamine release inside the individual's brain, the extent of which is contingent upon the specific drug used. This may exacerbate addiction by being linked to the sensation of gratification and reinforcement (Bromberg et al., 2010).

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Onset: Addiction often starts with the first encounter of substance use. Engaging in drug use due to factors like curiosity, peer pressure, or stress might serve as the first stage in the progression towards addiction.

Addiction is classified as a neurological disorder. Chemical alterations in the brain and disruptions in neurotransmitter levels play a role in the formation of addiction. The treatment of addiction is significantly influenced by spiritual and behavioral factors (Bromberg et al., 2010).

Therapy enhances an individual's abilities to cope with addiction and targets the fundamental psychological factors contributing to addiction. In addition, family therapy and motivational studies are also efficacious in addressing addiction.

Who Can Be Addicted?

Any individual may be impacted by addiction, and this process is influenced by several diverse circumstances. Several variables that might impact the level of addiction in individuals include:

Typically, addiction develops throughout adolescence or early adulthood. Adolescence has a significant risk of addiction, mostly owing to the exploration of personal identity and the impact of social influence (Dilbaz et al., 2019).

The variables influencing addiction development may vary among people, and each person's susceptibility to addiction differs. Nevertheless, it is crucial to acknowledge that addiction is a multifaceted phenomenon that involves the interaction of several components. Hence, it is essential to implement a range of strategies at both individual and societal levels in order to effectively prevent and address addiction (Dilbaz et al., 2019).

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Does Addiction End? Is Treatment Possible?

Addiction is a condition that may be effectively treated, and a significant number of individuals are capable of achieving successful recovery from addiction. Below are few essential aspects to consider while addressing addiction:

Drive and resolve: An individual's drive and resolve are crucial in overcoming addiction. The individual's receptiveness to therapy, along with self-motivation and a supportive environment, enhances the likelihood of achieving positive outcomes (Lussier and Richard, 2007).

Professional Help: Addressing addiction often requires the assistance of trained professionals. This may be achieved by a group that offers medical and psychological assistance. Medical practitioners, psychologists, therapists, and other healthcare experts provide guidance and support to those who are grappling with addiction.

Treatment Plan: Given the unique nature of each person's addiction experience, it is essential to tailor the treatment strategy to their specific needs. The treatment approach often consists of many elements, including detoxification, psychotherapy, drug therapy, and support groups (Köknel, 1998, p.251).

Detoxification: A digital diet, a term sometimes used interchangeably with digital detox, refers to the deliberate cessation of digital media consumption for a specific purpose, with the aim of attaining improved and more refined outcomes in certain activities (Skivko, et al; 2019:63).

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Detoxification is a method that may be used to alleviate the physiological manifestations of addiction. This procedure facilitates the body's elimination of the addictive drug.

Psychotherapy: Therapy is a method that may be used to comprehend and modify an individual's cognitive processes, emotional states, and actions. Developing ways to deal with addiction may be achieved by addressing the psychological issues of the person (Cüceler et al., 2022).

Medication: Medications may be administered in some instances to address addiction. These drugs may alleviate withdrawal symptoms caused by substance use or assist in managing mental and emotional problems linked with substance abuse (Cüceler et al., 2022).

Support Groups: assistance groups provide persons struggling with addiction the chance to exchange experiences with others and get reciprocal assistance. Support groups have the potential to enhance an individual's motivation and enhance their capacity to manage addiction (Fisher, 1995, Flores, 1997; as cited in Fisher, 2006, p.259-260).

Dependency may be effectively addressed, and a significant number of individuals can overcome their dependency via appropriate assistance and personal commitment. Nonetheless, the therapy procedure may be protracted and demanding, requiring ongoing assistance and adjustment to the treatment regimen.

Definition of Communication

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Individuals often engage in communication unconsciously. They may communicate by observing and interpreting the other person's motions, facial expressions, eye contact, and physical proximity. Nonverbal interactions refer to communication that takes place without the use of words. They may often be more impactful and influential than verbal communication.

Communication is the foundation of interpersonal interactions and plays a crucial role in all aspects of everyday life. Proficient communication abilities in both personal and professional connections contribute to the development of more robust and prosperous partnerships.

The Importance of Communication

Communication has been a need for humanity since ancient times. The cave drawings represent a kind of self-expression. Throughout history, a wide range of communication methods have been used, spanning from ancient times to the present, and many remain in use today. The evolution of communication technologies has occurred, although the fundamental need to engage in communication has remained constant over the course of history.

Individuals have an aversion to solitude. Consequently, he tries to cultivate favorable connections with his surroundings. He seeks solace from his own anguish by becoming a part of many groups. Individuals experience positive emotions and a sense of empowerment when they are in the company of others. According to Maslow's hierarchy of requirements, individuals assert that social needs come after fulfilling physiological needs (such as eating, drinking, housing, and breathing) and security needs (such as health, wellbeing, and financial stability). Organizations such as friends, family, communities, religious organizations, sports teams, and clubs play a crucial role in facilitating human connection. Being aware of the fact that you are cherished by others instills a sense of self-assurance in you. The significance of communication is an undeniable fact.

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Old Communication Tools

The internet has caused our globe to become smaller. Previously, obtaining news from an individual was not as easy as it is now. In ancient civilizations, information of battle was sent throughout the whole nation by igniting fires on the hills. The Indians were using the smoke vehicle. They were fashioning forms using a lid to shield the flames. The frequency of the smoke served as an indicator of the level of urgency in the issue. The use of writing by the Sumerians brought to a transformation in communication methods (Pekşen, 2019).

Revolution in Printed Media: Newspaper

Printed publications serve as a crucial medium for the purpose of reaching a wide audience and exerting influence on the public. According to Pekşen (2019), the first use of a newspaper occurred in Beijing in the year 700 AD.

A Turning Point: Telegraph

The world was introduced to a new method of communication with the advent of electric current transmissions. There are two lengthy transmitters. The process involves the transmission of encrypted communications between two transmitters, with the messages being sent from one transmitter to another. Letters and numerals possess distinct rhythms. Every stroke on the machine is distinct. By doing this, the recipient may transcribe the message. The invention of the electromagnetic telegraph by Samuel Morse was a significant milestone (Pekşen, 2019).

One of the Greatest Inventions of the Age: The Telephone

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It is the process of transferring sound from one location to another. On March 10, 1876, Alexander Graham Bell created it. The first mobile phone was created. Subsequently, there were advancements in telecommunications technology, including the development of radio wave, push-button phones, mobile phones, and smart phones (Pekşen, 2019).

Seeing the News: Television

Logie was established in the year 1923. The invention may be attributed to Baird. Following the transmission of the sound, the transmission of the picture began as well. Although originally limited to a small number of households, televisions are today ubiquitous, with every home possessing one or perhaps many units. After a fatiguing day at work, we relax and get pleasure from being informed about global events. It enables us to see the films and television programs that we have a strong affinity for (Pekşen, 2019).

The Last Point in the Revolution: Computer

The first computer, known as ENIAC, was unveiled under the backdrop of World War II. The object had a weight of 30 tons and dimensions comparable to those of a room. Initially, it was used for military applications. The first portable computer, the IBM 5100, was launched in September 1975 (Pekşen, 2019).

The Network That Surrounds the World: The Internet

The development of the first network for military applications began in 1969. ARPANET is an outcome of this. Following the conclusion of the conflicts, the internet underwent a process of commercialization. Through its commercialization, several advancements have integrated into our daily existence. For instance, platforms such as social networking, online training, or

online commerce. In the present era, it is possible to do all of our tasks using the internet. The internet allows us to readily access a vast array of entertainment, news, and information (Pekşen, 2019).

The Collapse of Family Relationships with Social Media

What effect does technology and game addiction have on family communication?

According to Binark and Bayraktutan (2008), the emergence of numerous ideas from game genres occurred in the mid-1980s with the advent of digital electronics, computer, and video games. This trend has continued, as stated by Özbek (2021).

The term "digital game" has been consistently used in academic literature from the mid-2000s. The idea of digital games encompasses console games, mobile games, and computer games (Buluş, Buluş, 2020).

Buluş (2020) characterizes digital games as a phenomena that is progressively used by individuals of many genders and age groups (Özbek, 2021).

According to Tran and Srutton (2013), online games provide possibilities for competitive and cooperative connection with other players, fulfilling the desire for enjoyment and occupying free time (Kuşay, Akbayır, 2015).

A survey was conducted among 250 parents to investigate the potential impact of digital and virtual games, as well as internet use, on their children's sleep habits and irritability. The findings revealed that 224 parents lacked understanding or awareness of this problem (Deldal, 2023).

A survey was conducted with 250 parents to investigate the prevalence of behavioral issues in children aged 0-6 who are exposed to computer games. The findings indicate that parents either lack awareness or show indifference towards this issue (Deldal, 2023).

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When questioned about their awareness of the negative impact of digital games and the internet on family communication, 241 out of 250 parents admitted to being uninformed, leading to the conclusion that they were completely unaware of this problem (Deldal, 2023).

Technology and gaming addiction have a detrimental impact on the language used in family interactions. Communication spans a broad spectrum, including both peaceful dialogue and aggressive behavior. The aforementioned study demonstrates that a lack of knowledge and awareness among families is a significant contributing element to the adverse effects of digital games and the internet on family communication processes, the escalation of aggression and hostility, and the rise in behavioral disorders.

CONCLUSION

Technological advancements have had an impact on the voting process. The advent of technology led to a shift in gaming from mostly outside activities to the use of technologies such as laptops and tablets.

Studies have shown that when games are compressed into computers, phones, and tablets, they have a detrimental impact on family interactions, lead to behavioral issues, disturb sleep patterns, and escalate anger and aggression.

It is crucial to acknowledge that the lack of understanding, apathy, and ignorance among families significantly contribute to behavioral problems, heightened irritation and aggressiveness, and detrimental impacts on intra-family communication.

What is required is to enhance the understanding of families on this matter, by conducting family and child seminars, limiting the duration of computer and digital game use, and promoting the engagement in traditional and group games instead.

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Promoting the engagement in these games will mitigate the potential negative impact on family communication, behavioral issues, and the adoption of communication styles including rage and violence.

RESTRICTION

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RESOURCES

Berkay Buluş, GC (2020). Digital games and digital economy as culture industry. Aksaray University Faculty of Economics and Administrative Sciences Journal, 12(2), 1-6.

Bevilacqua , L., Goldman, D. (2009). Genes and addictions . Clinical Pharmacology and Therapeutics , 85(4), 359.

Binark , M. B. (2008). Digital gaming as culture industry. Istanbul: Kalkedon Publishing.
Caillois, R. (1961). Man, lay and games . Champaign : Illinois Press .

- Borsos , D. (2009). Addiction , models of. In GL Fisher, & NA Roget , Encyclopedia of substances abuse prevention , treatment and recovery (p. 10-14). California: Sage Publications. Bostanci, N. (2005). Stigma towards individuals with mental disorders and practices to reduce it. The Thinking Man Journal of Psychiatry and Neurology Sciences 2005;18:32-38, 18(1), 32-38.
- Bromberg , M., Ethan , S., Matsumoto , M., & Hikosaka , O. (2010). Dopamine in motivational control : Rewarding , aversive and alerting . Neuron , 68(5), 815-834.
- Cüceler, Türkleş, Yılmaz, 2022, Psychosocial Problems Experienced by Substance Addicted Individuals, Applied Evidence-Based Interventions and the Role of Nursing, Journal of Addiction 2022;23(1):105-110
- Deldal , 2023, Cognitive Development Problems and Digital Games in Children as a Health Problem, Istanbul Medisosal Education and Research Journal of Health Sciences, United Kingdom
- Demircan, Tutam, 2024. A View of Substance Use Disorder from a Family Perspective, Journal of Addiction; 25(3):1-1.
- Dilbaz N, Darçın A, et al., (2019), Substance Use Risk and Protection from Substance Addiction, Ankara.
- Fisher, MS . (2006). Handbook of social work with groups . Garvin , C.D. , Gutierrez , ML, Galinsky , MJ (Eds.), Groups for substance abuse in treatment (259-274). New York : The Guildoff Pres.
- Green Crescent(2024), What is Addiction? , <https://www.yesilay.org.tr/tr/bagimlikte/bagimlikte-nedir>
- Güleç, V. (2024), The Collapse of Family Relations with Social Media, <https://dergipark.org.tr/en/download/article-file/443874>

Günüç S, Yiğit E (2024), Determination of Family Profiles According to Children's Digital Game Addiction, <https://dergipark.org.tr/en/download/article-file/983060>

Hamamcı, Şahin, Türk, 2022, The Relationship between Depression, Anxiety and Stress Coping Attitudes and Social Media Addiction During the Covid-19 Pandemic, Erciyes Communication Magazine, e-ISSN: 2667-5811

Internet Help(2024), What are the Positive Effects of Digital Games?
<https://www.internetyardim.org.tr/dijital-oyunlar/dijital-oyunlarin-olumlu-etkileri-nedir>

Köknel, Ö. (1998). Dependence. Istanbul: Golden Books

Kuşay Yeliz, AZ (2015). Journey to consumption with digital games: "A research on child users in terms of learning approach". Akdeniz University Faculty of Communication Journal, 0(23), 135-154.

Lokman Hekim University(2024), What is Addiction?
<https://www.lokmanhekim.edu.tr/ozgur-koy-tedavi-ve-rehabilitasyon-merkezi/bagimlikte-rehberi#>

Lussier, M . and Richard, C. (2007). the motivational Interview . Communication Tips , (53), 2117-2118.

Ministry of Family and Social Services (2024), Social and Economic Rights and Duties,
<https://www.aile.gov.tr/eyhgm/mevzuat/ulusal-mevzuat/anayasa/#:~:text=Madde%2041%20%E2%80%93%20Aile%2C%20T%C3%BCrk%20society%20take%20%20measures%2C%20%C5%9Fkilat%C4%B1%20establish%20>.

Özbek, 2021, Relationship between Digitalized Games and ADHD, Istanbul

Pekşen D.(2024), Communication Types and Communication Tools,
<https://www.iienstitu.com/blog/iletisim-turleri-ve-iletisim-araclari>

Positive and Negative Effects of Digital Games (2024),
<https://www.guvenliweb.org.tr/dosya/wXK68.pdf>

Skivko , M., Korneeva , E., and Kolmykova , M., (2019). Digital Minimalism as a Leading Limitation of Media Communications in the Heyday of Digital Culture . In Proceedings of the 6th International Conference on Social , Economic , and Academic Leadership (ICSEAL-6-2019) (pp . 225-229).

Straussner , S. (2004). Assessment and treatment of clients with alcohol and other drug abuse problems : An overview . In S. L. Straussner , Clinical work with Substance-Abusing Clients (pp. 3- 36). New York: The Guildford press

Supreme Council for Fighting Addiction (2024), What is Addiction? <https://bmyk.gov.tr/TR-67179/bagimliđi-nedir.html>

TR Ministry of National Education, (2011). Family and Consumer Services, Ankara.

Tran , G. A. (2013). “ What factors affect consumer acceptance of in -game advertisements ?”. Journal Of Advertising Research . 53(4), 455-469.

Turkish Language Association (2024), What is family? , <http://www.tdk.gov.tr/>

Varan, Ö (2024), What are Family Types, <https://npistanbul.com/aile-universitesi/aile-tipleri-nelerin>

Volkow , N. D. (2010). Drugs , brains , and behavior : The science of addiction Retrieved on March , 23, (2011), 255-169. <https://nida.nih.gov/sites/default/files/soa.pdf>. Access date: 14.03.2022.

CURRENT SCIENCE

Wikipedia (2024), Video Game Genre, https://tr.wikipedia.org/wiki/Video_oyunu_t%C3%BCr%C3%BC

World Health Organization ICD-11 for Mortality and Morbidity Statistics (2021). Disorders due to addictive behaviors .
<https://icd.who.int/browse11/lm/en#/http://id.who.int/icd/entity/499894965>